

Water saturation deficit, leaf rolling, and desiccation tolerance of rice as affected by rooting depth and leaf area.^a

Rooting depth (cm)	Leaf area (%)	WSD ^b (%)	Leaf rolling (1-5) ^c	Desiccation ^d tolerance (1-9)	Root zone moisture (%)
5	100	86.0 a	5.0 a	9.0 a	4.0 c
5	50	71.0 b	5.0 a	9.0 a	6.0 c
10	100	50.0 c	5.0 a	8.0 a	6.0 bc
10	50	31.0 d	4.0 a	7.0 a	8.0 ab
15	100	25.0 de	3.0 b	7.0 a	8.0 a
15	50	7.0 f	2.0 e	1.0 c	9.0 a
Control	100	15.0 ef	3.0 b	4.0 b	10.0 a
Control	50	6.0 f	2.0 c	1.0 c	9.0 a
CV (%)		23	11	20	16

^aFigures with the same letter(s) do not differ significantly at the 1% level.

^bWSD (water saturation deficit) (%) = $\frac{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{field weight}}{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{oven-dry weight}} \times 100$.

^cRated on a 1-5 scale where 1 = no leaf rolling and 5 = leaves severely rolled. ^dRated on a 1-9 scale where 1 = no desiccation of leaves and 9 = leaves severely desiccated.

seeded. Seedlings were sprinkled with water for the first 3 wk. The leaf area was clipped to half at 21 d after seeding.

The internal water stress of the leaves was expressed as the water saturation deficit

percentage (WSD%), defined as water deficiency relative to when a leaf was 100% turgid in water. This was measured gravimetrically. The WSD% increased with decrease in rooting depth (see table).

The soil moisture percentage around the root zone decreased as rooting depth decreased. Soil moisture was also reduced with increased leaf area, but only at 5- and 10-cm rooting depths. At 15 cm or deeper, leaf area did not affect the root zone moisture.

Like rooting depth, the leaf area also significantly determines the plant's internal water balance as well as its desiccation tolerance. However, the degrees of leaf rolling and leaf desiccation were significantly reduced with decreased leaf area at 15 cm rooting depth or more. At 5- and 10-cm rooting depths, leaf rolling as well as desiccation tolerance were statistically similar at 100% and 50% leaf area.

Thus, less leaf area is more important at greater rooting depths than at shallower rooting depths when desiccation tolerance of a variety is considered. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Tolerance for Al toxicity in lowland rice

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A major production constraint in acid upland soils is Al toxicity. So far, screening rices for Al tolerance has been limited to upland cultivars. However, lowland rice is grown on about 2 million ha with acid sulfate soil conditions. These rices are prone to Al toxicity during dry spells. Several Al-tolerant upland rices have been identified, but their use in acid lowlands as cultivars or as donors for breeding purposes is very limited because they are japonicas.

Previous investigations showed that relative root length (RRL) of 2-wk-old seedlings (determined as the ratio of root length in a nutrient solution with 30 ppm Al to the root length in a normal nutrient solution) is a good criterion for selecting Al-tolerant genotypes. With the objective of isolating Al-tolerant lowland indicas, we used this technique to screen 62 cultivars originating from acid sulfate soil areas of

India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, and West Africa.

The experiment, which was laid out in a randomized complete block design with two replications, was conducted in an IRRRI Phytotron glasshouse with 29/21 °C day/night temperatures and 70% relative humidity. IRAT104 was used as the tolerant check and IR1552 as the susceptible check. Eight seedlings were sampled for each test entry in a replication.

The differential tolerance for Al among cultivars was found highly significant (see table). RRL ranged from 0.45 in S-4 to 1.16 in Siyam Kuning. The RRL was 0.83 for tolerant check IRAT104 and 0.57 for susceptible check IR1552. In 17 varieties, RRL was 1.0 or more, indicating that Al did not affect the root growth of these cultivars. Other researchers earlier reported increases in root length and growth of seedlings of tolerant cultivars when exposed to added Al.

The difference in RRL means between tolerant check IRAT104 and the two best performing test varieties (Siyam Kuning and Gudabang Putih) was highly significant. This finding suggests that the tolerance of these two cultivars is very much

Relative root length of some traditional rice varieties grown in normal and Al toxic nutrient solution.

Variety	Origin	Relative root length ^a
Siyam Kuning	Indonesia	1.16
Gudabang Putih	Indonesia	1.14
Siyam	Indonesia	1.10
Lemo	Indonesia	1.09
Khao Daeng	Thailand	1.08
Siyamhalus	Indonesia	1.06
Bjm-12	Indonesia	1.06
Ketan	Indonesia	1.06
Seribu Gantang	Malaysia	1.05
Bayar Raden Rati	Indonesia	1.05
Padi Kanji	Indonesia	1.04
Bjm-13	Indonesia	1.04
Batang Pane	Indonesia	1.04
Bjm-14	Indonesia	1.04
Ca Dung Do	Vietnam	1.04
Bjm-10	Indonesia	1.04
Padi Jambi	Indonesia	1.03
Gablak Cablak	Indonesia	0.96
Barito	Indonesia	0.94
Engatek	Malaysia	0.93
Bjm-15	Indonesia	0.93
Siyam Kuning	Indonesia	0.93
Quisidugo	West Africa	0.93
Lua Thuoc	Vietnam	0.92
Gudabang Kuning	Indonesia	0.92
Bjm-17	Indonesia	0.90
Kutik Putih	Indonesia	0.90
Kapuas	Indonesia	0.89
Baiang 6	Indonesia	0.89
Pontianak	Indonesia	0.85

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Table continued

Variety	Origin	Relative root length ^a
Nang Coi	Vietnam	0.85
Bayar Kuning	Indonesia	0.85
Bjm-11	Indonesia	0.85
Thung Hoa Binh	Vietnam	0.85
Alabio	Indonesia	0.81
Khao Seetha	Thailand	0.81
Gaw Diaw Bow	Indonesia	0.80
Khao Taeng	Thailand	0.80
Lua Thuoc Co	Vietnam	0.79
Talang A	Indonesia	0.78
Mahakam	Indonesia	0.78
Galambong	Indonesia	0.77
Tai Nguyen	Vietnam	0.77
Ketambar	Indonesia	0.74
Thom Ran	Vietnam	0.74
Talang B	Indonesia	0.73
Duvi Trau	Vietnam	0.70
Can Dung Phen	Vietnam	0.70
Gogo Ranceh	Indonesia	0.70
Doc Phung	Vietnam	0.68
Nang Gao	Vietnam	0.67
Mansirit	Indonesia	0.67
Kapus	Indonesia	0.66
Yaca	West Africa	0.66
S-1	West Africa	0.66
Atanha	West Africa	0.62
Nang Co	Vietnam	0.62
Than Nang Do	Vietnam	0.62
Pokkali	India	0.62
Soc Nau	Vietnam	0.59
Silla	West Africa	0.57
S-4	West Africa	0.45
IRAT104 (tolerant check)		0.83
IR1552 (susceptible check)		0.57
CV (%)		12.5
LSD (0.05)		0.21
LSD (0.01)		0.28

^a Mean of two replications.

higher than that of IRAT104. Varieties Siyam, Lemo, Khao Daeng, Siyamhalus, Bjm-12, Ketan, Seribu Gantang, Bayar Raden Rati, and Padi Kanji also produced significantly higher RRLs than did IRAT104. The tolerance level of the other cultivars was comparable with that of IRAT104. Only three of the 62 varieties expressed sensitivity.

The results indicated that tolerance for Al toxicity exists in lowland varieties grown on acid sulfate soils. The cultivars that are more tolerant of Al than upland cultivar IRAT104 may be good donors for breeding Al-tolerant lowland rice varieties. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1, a short-duration hybrid for Karnataka, India

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Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1 (KRH-1) is a short-duration rice hybrid selected at RRS from rice hybrids shared by IRRI through the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. Its parents are cytoplasmic male sterile line IR58025 A and restorer line IR9761-19-1 R.

KRH-1 matures in 125 d and is 90-cm tall. It produces an average of 460 panicles/m² and 168 grains/panicle. The grains are long-slender and straw-colored, the kernels

are white, and the 1,000-grain weight is 23.3 g. It is for use in the irrigated areas of Karnataka. The recommended fertilizer dose for KRH-1 is 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. The seed rate is 20 kg/ha with single seedlings per hill at 20 × 10-cm spacing.

KRH-1 recorded a yield advantage of 1.5 t/ha over check Mangala in trials conducted during 1990-93 at Mandya (see table). Similar results were obtained in multilocation trials and in 100 on-farm trials around Karnataka, in which KRH-1 yielded an average 6.8 t/ha with a yield advantage of 1.5 t/ha over Mangala. KRH-1 has moderate resistance to neck blast, sheath rot, and stem borer.

The State Variety Release Committee released KRH-1 during 1994 for cultivation in Karnataka State. ■

Mean yield (t/ha) of Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1 (KRH-1) in different trials in Karnataka, India. 1990-93.

Type of trial	Year	Trials (no.)	KRH-1	Mangala (check)	Yield advantage
Research station (Mandya)	1990-93	10	7.2	5.7	1.5
Multilocation	1991-93	18	5.3	3.7	1.6
On-farm	1991-93	100	6.8	5.3	1.5
Demonstration	1993	10	6.3	5.0	1.3
Mean			6.4	4.9	1.5

Xiangyou 63, a quasi-aromatic hybrid rice with good quality and high yield

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Xiangyou 63 was developed at HHRRC using aromatic cytoplasmic male sterile line Xiangxiang 2 A and nonaromatic restorer line Minghui 63. It was released to farmers in Jan 1995. Xiangyou 63 is the first quasi-aromatic hybrid rice in China, and Xiangxiang 2A, developed from the cross V20A/N20 B/MR365 by HHRRC, is the first aromatic CMS line in China. The hybrid has so far been planted on more than 20,000 ha and seems popular with farmers and consumers. In addition to being aromatic, the hybrid has good grain quality, high-yielding ability, good disease resistance, and wide adaptability.

The hybrid, which produces only some aromatic grains on each plant, has some advantages over aromatic inbred or hybrid rices. In China, aromatic inbred and hybrid rices are usually mixed before cooking with nonaromatic rice to lessen their intense aroma. Xiangyou 63 grain, however, is already mixed due to F₂ segregation.

Another advantage is that its grains are not as easily attacked by insect pests and rats as are those of aromatic rices, and that it is also relatively easier to store than aromatic rice.

All of Xiangyou 63's quality characters, except brown rice percentage, meet the first and second class standards of fine quality rice issued by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (Table 1). It has been endorsed as a fine quality rice in Hunan, Guangdong, Yunnan, Guizhou, Shaanxi, and Henan provinces.

Xiangyou 63 yielded an average of about 6.9 t/ha in various trials during 1987-89. For example, in the 1988-89 Hunan